

THE FORMATION OF THE GENERAL LEVEL OF LEAVES IN THE RIDGES AND FAMILIES CREATED AS A RESULT OF SELECTIVE RESEARCH

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Annotation: According to the results of the research carried out in the article, it is scientifically based that the total level of leaves in all ridges and families decreases in different degrees in the conditions of water deficit (0-1-0) compared to the optimal irrigation (1-2-1) system on non-saline soils.

Keywords: family, ridge, photosynthesis, level of leaves, water deficit.

Introduction: The leaf of green plants is one of the most important organs in which the process of photosynthesis takes place. That is why the leaf is called the main photosynthetic organ. Its cellular structure is adapted to transpiration, respiration and mainly photosynthesis. The study of leaf parameters in plants is of great importance in classifying life processes of plants, especially photosynthetic properties. The accumulation of organic matter necessary for the formation of the crop depends on the intensity of photosynthesis (the time of assimilation activity of the cotton leaf surface and the increase of nutrients in each bush and per unit area). Optimum leaf surface area and duration of leaf function are factors that determine yield. The size of the leaf surface can vary depending on the characteristics of the cotton type, the external environment, the thickness of the bush, the amount of feeding, the moisture content of the soil, and the planting method. The cotton leaf surface reaches its maximum size during flowering and harvest [4; p. 34]. There are about 955 organic substances in plant dry matter, which are formed as a result of the process of photosynthesis. Most of the organic matter in plants is used for the formation of reproductive parts. Generally, plant yield depends primarily on net photosynthetic productivity, leaf surface area, duration of assimilation period, amount of organic matter used for respiration, and external and internal factors. The

productivity of agricultural crops is not only related to the variety, the technology of its cultivation, but there is a correct connection between the productivity of the crop and the level of leaves, the duration of its operation. The level of leaves, duration of operation, accumulation of dry mass determines the photosynthetic productivity of the field [1; p. 20].

Changes in cotton symptoms under water deficit conditions depend on the biological characteristics of the variety and the sensitivity of the plants. Morphological characters controlled by one or more genes change little. Agricultural traits controlled by many genes, such as yield, ripening speed, fiber length, quality, tissue water content, and their water holding properties, are more variable [3; 5-27 p.].

In our research, important physiological indicators - total water content in leaves, water holding properties and transpiration speed were determined, and the sign of the general level of leaves, calculated from the growth point, was also studied. In the conditions of non-saline soils, in our research in the optimal irrigation system, the highest indicators of the total level of the leaves were studied in the period of gross ripening, of which 29.7 dm² and 26.4 dm² were recorded in families O-17-19 and O-95-96, which showed the highest indicators (see Table 1). The lowest indicator was observed to be 21.9 dm² in the O-10-11 family. The leaves of the T-14-16/14 ridge created as a result of these experiments showed a total area of 25.9 dm². If the total surface area of the leaves of the families grown under water shortage conditions was 16.4-25.1 dm² on average, while in the T-14-16/14 ridge, this indicator is 18.8 dm², and in S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated as a sample variety, this indicator was 17.9, 21.5 dm², respectively, which indicates that the overall level of the leaves is somewhat smaller compared to the experiments planted in the optimal irrigation system.

In the next year of our research, the total surface of the leaves of the families planted in the conditions of non-saline soils, optimal irrigation system is 19.4-24.9 dm² on average, it was observed that the S-6524 variety planted as a model variety

had 24.8 dm², and An-Boyovut-2 variety had 16.9 dm². In the T-14-16/14 range separated as a result of research, this indicator was 24.2 dm².

Table 1

**Total leaf surface formation of cotton varieties, ridges and plant families
(dm²)**

Family, ridge and model varieties	Non-saline soil conditions (Tashkent)		Saline soil conditions (Syr Darya)	
	optimal watering	water shortage	optimal watering	water shortage
2016 year				
O-95-96	26,4±2,4	19,2±3,6	25,1±2,1	18,1±2,9
O-23-24	25,7±2,5	25,1±6,9	24,9±2,3	23,7±4,7
O-97-99	23,9±4,7	19,5±4,5	23,0±4,5	18,2±3,4
O-10-11	21,9±2,3	16,4±2,4	21,2±2,8	16,6±2,6
O-12-14	23,4±4,1	20,9±3,6	23,9±2,7	18,7±2,9
O-17-19	29,7±3,8	23,8±0,7	28,4±2,4	21,4±2,2
T-14-16/14	25,9±2,2	18,8±2,0	25,1±2,3	18,1±2,4
C-6524	22,7±2,6	17,9±1,7	22,4±2,5	18,4±2,5
An-Boyovut-2	24,2±2,7	21,5±2,4	23,8±2,1	21,2±2,6
2017 year				
O-95-96	23,8±2,0	16,1±3,4	23,2±2,3	15,2±2,3
O-23-24	24,8±1,6	18,0±3,3	23,6±2,5	17,2±2,7
O-97-99	23,3±2,4	19,8±2,2	23,9±1,7	18,6±2,5
O-10-11	22,5±3,6	17,5±3,0	21,9±2,2	16,2±2,8
O-12-14	19,4±1,3	14,7±2,3	21,2±1,4	14,1±2,9
O-17-19	21,0±2,3	19,2±3,4	22,3±1,9	17,9±3,1
T-14-16/14	24,2±2,0	18,2±3,3	24,9±4,2	19,4±2,7
C-6524	24,8±1,6	22,7±2,6	24,4±2,4	22,2±2,4

An-Boyovut-2	16,9±1,3	15,4±1,4	17,5±2,1	15,0±1,7
2018 year				
O-95-96	23,7±4,2	18,9±0,6	22,3±2,1	17,3±1,2
O-23-24	24,9±0,5	18,2±2,3	23,7±1,7	16,9±1,7
O-97-99	26,4±6,3	23,7±2,7	25,2±4,1	22,4±1,9
O-10-11	24,8±2,6	20,5±4,3	23,9±1,7	19,2±2,5
O-12-14	24,4±6,2	18,0±4,6	23,7±2,3	17,2±2,2
O-17-19	25,8±1,9	23,7±4,2	24,9±1,6	21,4±2,7
T-14-16/14	28,0±4,6	21,2±2,7	27,5±2,5	20,1±2,1
C-6524	25,2±2,7	19,9±3,7	24,8±2,2	18,5±1,9
An-Boyovut-2	18,9±0,6	15,8±2,7	18,1±1,4	14,2±1,8

In the conditions of water shortage, the average compared surface volume of leaves in families is 14.7-19.8 dm², in the T-14-16/14 ridge, this indicator was 18.2 dm² on average, and in S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated as a model variety, this indicator was 22.7, 15.4 dm², respectively. In saline soil conditions, optimal irrigation system, the average compared surface area of leaves in families is 21.9-23.6 dm², in the separated ridge it is 24.9 dm², and it was found that in S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated as a sample variety, it was 24.4, 14.7 dm², respectively. In the third year of our research, in our families created as a result of research, in the optimal irrigation system (1-2-1) on non-saline soils, the average compared surface area of leaves was 23.7-26.4 dm², and in the conditions of saline soils it is on average 18.0-23.7 dm², it was observed that the relative compared surface area of leaves was lower by 5.7-2.7 dm², respectively, compared to the optimal irrigation system (1-2-1). In our research, it was determined that S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties, which participated as model varieties, the average compared surface area of leaves was 25.2, 18.9 dm² in the optimal irrigation system (1-2-1), and 19.9, 15.8 dm² in water shortage conditions, respectively. It was noted that the average compared surface volume of leaves in families with saline soil conditions and optimal irrigation system was 22.2-25.2 dm², while in water-

scarce conditions, this indicator was 6.9-22.4 dm² in families. It was observed that in the sample S-6524 and An-Boyovut-2 varieties involved in the research, it was 24.8 and 18.4 dm² under optimal irrigation system, and 18.5-14.4 dm² under water shortage conditions, respectively. The photosynthetic potential of the crop combines two main indicators, the leaf surface and the duration of its operation. According to Stroganova, [2; 5-p.] it is desirable to determine the leaf surface in experiments depending on the conditions of cultivation and planting period.

Conclusion: On the basis of the above data, it can be concluded that in our research, the total level of leaves in all rows and families is reduced to a different extent in water deficit (0-1-0) conditions compared to the optimal irrigation (1-2-1) system option in non-saline soils. Our results on the sign of the general level of leaves in plants show that the adaptation of plants to water deficit occurs due to the change of different elements of the photosynthetic apparatus, including the number of leaves. In the conditions of water shortage, it was determined that the total amount of water in the leaves of the cotton plant, the decrease in the rate of transpiration, the water retention properties of the leaves, the increase in the total surface of the leaves and the number of stomata per unit of leaf surface are the important physiological and morphological mechanisms of adaptation of the plants of the ridge and families to this stress factor. As a result of the research, it was proved that the isolated ridges and families are superior in water deficit tolerance traits.

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